

ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COMBATING CARBON DIOXIDE EMITS AND FINANCIAL INDICATORS OF INDUSTRIAL SECTORS OF THE ECONOMY FROM FOREIGN COUNTRIES

Tillyakhodzhaev Muzaffarkhoja Abdupatakhovich

Main expert of the Center for the Development of Seed Production at Ministry of
Agriculture Of the Republic of Uzbekistan doctor of economics, professor

Muratkulov Olimjon Komiljonovich

Head of the technology and marketing transfer department at the Uzbekistan-
Japan youth innovation center

olimjonmuratkulov9@gmail.com

Maksudova Shakhista Yakubovna

Professor.

shakhista@mail.ru

Orolov Jorabek Abdurahmon ogli

Assistant Lecturer of the Department of Nuclear power plants and thermal
power engineering, Faculty of power engineering, Tashkent State Technical

University orolovjorabek3@gmail.com

Khadjayev Ilkhom Amanovich

Tashkent State Technical University named after Islam Karimov, Faculty of Oil
and Gas. PhD associate Professor of the department of "Industrial economics and
management"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17434060>

Abstract: This article states that international policies to limit carbon dioxide emissions in mining enterprises create significant risks and opportunities for industrial companies, while relatively high-emission production processes are sensitive to uncertain costs associated with carbon dioxide emissions and may reflect inefficiency in production. Analyzing the effectiveness of the fight against carbon dioxide emissions from 2002 to 2025, we calculated 1,776 firms that demonstrated the best financial performance over approximately years.

Keywords: Carbon efficiency, carbon dioxide emissions, production efficiency, industrial enterprises, mining industry, efficient resource use, financial indicators, systemic risk, utility and profitability, international environmental policy, risk management, energy efficiency

Introduction. International policy measures to limit carbon emissions pose significant risks and opportunities for companies. The main risk, commonly referred to as carbon risk, is related to the uncertainty of future carbon costs. International commitments to combat climate change require additional regulatory measures such as carbon pricing, subsidies, fines, and product requirements (Busch and Hoffmann, 2017; IPCC, 2021). These measures imply that carbon emissions are becoming an important part of the costs of companies.

At the same time, the transition to a low-carbon economy can create competitive opportunities, ranging from comparative advantages to innovation and increased environmental efficiency.

1. Carbon efficiency and financial performance hypotheses:

To provide a rich understanding of the relationship between carbon efficiency and financial performance, we discuss short and long-term performance aspects as well as effects on firm risk. Therefore, we test whether carbon efficiency positively relates to short-term accounting-based operating performance, measured as return on assets (ROA): **H₁**. Carbon efficiency is positively related to return on assets. Apart from its association with short-term profits, industrial firms' carbon efficiency may affect long-term performance expectations as reflected in market valuations. In this respect, a deep-rooted belief in the corporate finance literature and practice is that activities directed at reducing environmental impact impair firms market value if management departs from the objective to maximize shareholder value (Jensen and Meckling, 1977). **H₂**. Carbon efficiency is positively related to Tobin's Q. A growing stream of literature theorizes that good environmental performance has cash-flow preserving effects (Artis et al., 2019; Chilli, 2012; Layinos et al., 2013; Sharon and Natan, 2008). Laser et al. (2017) argue that high-CSR firms have stronger stakeholder relations, a form of social capital that provides insurance against event risk. **H₃**. Carbon efficiency is negatively related to systematic risk. Therefore, we further investigate the relationship of carbon efficiency with total risk, which is measured as the standard deviation of stock returns and thereby encompasses systematic and idiosyncratic risk.

2. Measuring carbon efficiency using a directional distance function.

This section introduces our measure of carbon efficiency and discusses its relevance as an indicator of environmental performance. We also provide a brief background to data envelopment analysis (DEA) and the directional distance function (DDF) approach on which our measure is based.

2.1. Carbon emissions in a directional distance function model.

The traditional measurement of technical efficiency typically ignores negative external effects from production (economic bads), such as carbon emissions, given the absence of price signals driving allocation (Koytodor, 1951, p. 38). However, the modeling of such bad outputs (as they are typically referred to in the environmental efficiency literature) now represents a growing field of interest in efficiency analysis (Kiyit and Soder, 2014; Jylil et al., 2018).

Fig. 1. Carbon efficiency in a directional distance function model.

We adapt the DDF model by specifying a direction vector $d = (-dx, dyg, -dyb) = (0,0,1) = (0,0,-yb)$. As such, we adopt a bad output minimizing approach, in which DMUs are evaluated in the direction of the bad output (yb), carbon emissions.

3. Carbon efficiency and financial performance.

We estimate the effect of carbon efficiency on financial performance using the following panel regression model:

$$Financial\ performance_{it} = \alpha + \beta Carbon\ efficiency_{it-1} + \gamma Resource\ efficiency_{it-1} + \delta'X_{it-1} + \Lambda + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

where $Financial\ performance_{it}$ is the measure of firm i 's financial performance at time t . Note that we lag the independent variables to ensure they are available when financial performance is measured and to be in line with the related literature (Dart Hoaus et al., 2019 Zema, 2013). Finally, we obtain a measure of total risk, which is the annualized standard deviation of total returns from end-of-June of year $t-1$ until end-of-June of year t , expressed in %. Note that the one-year lag specification in Eq.

Table 1

Summary statistics of efficiency and financial variables. Variable definitions are included in Appendix A.3.

	(1) N	(2) Mean	(3) Median	(4) StDev	(5) Min	(6) Max	(7) Skewness	(8) Kurtosis
<i>Efficiency estimates (2008-2016)</i>								
Carbon efficiency (0 to 1)	7800	0.31	0.12	0.38	0.00	1.00	1.02	2.35
Resource efficiency (0 to 1)	7796	0.56	0.50	0.30	0.02	1.00	0.21	1.70
Capital (mln USD)	7800	8417.54	2576.53	18869.89	1.69	263593.69	6.06	54.15
Labor (employees)	7800	42841.31	17931.00	72135.78	28.00	2200000.00	6.46	118.50
Energy (TJ)	7800	54469.67	5750.92	217159.41	1.48	6073969.00	13.14	253.74
Good output (mln USD)	7800	17128.57	6908.00	31624.26	10.62	476294.00	5.45	48.12
Bad output (Mt CO ₂ e)	7800	3.88	0.20	12.73	0.00	176.00	6.82	64.03
<i>Financial performance outcomes (2009-2017)</i>								
ROA (%)	7689	5.79	5.46	7.71	-73.23	37.00	-1.61	19.39
Tobin's Q	7489	1.87	1.66	0.81	-0.35	7.00	2.21	10.87
Systematic risk	7657	0.87	0.83	0.46	-0.14	2.34	0.49	3.19
Total risk (%)	7657	32.14	29.04	13.35	14.11	89.34	1.41	5.30
<i>Baseline control variables (2008-2016)</i>								
Size	7800	16.07	16.04	1.33	11.75	18.58	-0.08	2.58
Leverage (%)	7800	26.61	25.17	16.05	0.00	96.13	0.68	3.87
B/M	7511	0.70	0.56	0.61	-0.26	6.85	3.38	23.66

4. Data.

We obtain data on inputs, outputs, and other variables from Thomson Reuters Asset4 and Bloomberg for all firms with available data. Table 1 summarizes the main variables as well as the inputs and outputs used to construct the carbon efficiency and resource efficiency measures. The bad output (to be minimized) is Scope 1 carbon emissions in megatonnes (Mt) of CO_{2e}.¹⁶ We focus on direct Scope 1 emissions, given our purpose to identify heterogeneity in production processes. In this respect, Scope 1 emissions are the closest to the production process and under the direct control of firm management; by contrast, Scopes 2 and 3 emissions can much more readily be adjusted without substantial long-term changes to production activities (Busch and Lewandowski, 2018).

Fig. 2. Number of non-financial firms reporting Scope 1 CO_{2e} emissions, with available data on good output and inputs.

Fig. 2 shows the number of firms reporting Scope 1 emission data and for which data are available on the good output and inputs. We follow the sampling procedure of Trinks et al. (2020), which focuses on the period 2008–2016, due to quantity and quality of carbon emission reporting, and addresses extreme observations of carbon emissions in a systematic and conservative manner. In short, this procedure amounts to excluding zero reported emissions, firms with extreme emission figures resulting from unconsolidated reporting, and firms with extreme year-on-year changes in emission intensity.

Table 2.

Pairwise correlations between carbon efficiency, resource efficiency, factor inputs and outputs, and single-factor carbon intensity (2002–2024). Variable definitions are included in Appendix A.3. All correlation coefficients except (2):(3) and (3):(9) are significant at the 7% level.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
--	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----

Carbon efficiency (1)	1.00								
Resource efficiency (2)	0.64	1.00							
Capital (3)	-0.06	-0.01	1.00						
Labor (4)	-0.06	-0.04	0.32	1.00					
Energy (5)	-0.09	-0.06	0.41	0.10	1.00				
Good output (6)	0.03	0.09	0.73	0.60	0.33	1.00			
Bad output (7)	-0.12	-0.09	0.58	0.11	0.54	0.39	1.00		
Carbon intensity (8)	-0.16	-0.15	0.06	-0.08	0.17	-0.06	0.40	1.00	

5. Results.

This section first summarizes the carbon efficiency estimates. Then, we report the results regarding the impact of carbon efficiency on financial performance.

5.1. Carbon efficiency.

Table 1 summarizes the carbon efficiency scores and the financial performance variables used in the main analysis. The average carbon efficiency score is 0.49, which implies that the level of carbon emissions per unit of output of the average firm is 79% higher than the sector-year efficient peer. Hence, when we focus on carbon emissions only, firms seem to exhibit substantial differences in emissions generated from similar production (input-good output) structures.

Table 3

Carbon efficiency and financial performance (2009–2017). The estimated equation is: $\text{Financial performance}_{it} = \alpha + \beta \text{Carbon efficiency}_{it-1} + \gamma \text{Resource efficiency}_{it-1} + \delta X_{it-1} + \Lambda + \varepsilon_{it}$ (Eq. (1)). Financial performance represents return on assets (ROA) (columns (1) and (2)), Tobin's Q (columns (3) and (4)), systematic risk (columns (5) and (6)), and total risk (columns (7) and (8)). Carbon efficiency is a firm's efficiency with respect to Scope 1 CO₂e emissions, i.e., the ratio of projected to actual carbon emission levels. It is determined by the DDF model described in Appendix A.1 using a direction vector $d = (0, 0, -yb)$.

	ROA (1)	(2)	Tobin's Q (3)	(4)	Systematic risk (5)	(6)	Total risk (7)	(8)
Carbon efficiency	0.597* (0.333)	0.554 (0.340)	0.036 (0.037)	0.054 (0.037)	-0.048*** (0.017)	-0.032* (0.017)	-0.464 (0.503)	-0.535 (0.508)
Resource efficiency		0.092 (0.436)		-0.037 (0.051)		-0.031 (0.023)		0.176 (0.683)
Size	-0.060 (0.142)	-0.062 (0.142)	-0.133*** (0.016)	-0.133*** (0.016)	0.013** (0.007)	0.014** (0.007)	-2.241*** (0.200)	-2.243*** (0.201)
Leverage	-0.048*** (0.012)	-0.048*** (0.012)	-0.006*** (0.001)	-0.006*** (0.001)	0.001** (0.001)	0.001** (0.001)	0.116*** (0.018)	0.117*** (0.018)
B/M					0.048*** (0.012)	0.048*** (0.012)	1.806*** (0.327)	1.810*** (0.327)
N	7689	7685	7489	7485	7430	7427	7430	7427
Adj. R ²	0.122	0.122	0.291	0.291	0.433	0.433	0.483	0.483

6. Conclusion and discussion.

We employ a productive efficiency perspective to evaluate firms' carbon emission levels relative to those of best-practice (efficient) peers with comparable production activities. Specifically, based on a directional distance function (DDF) model, we construct a measure of carbon efficiency that reflects the percentage by which carbon emissions can be reduced in a given input-good output structure. We examine how carbon efficiency relates to various financial performance outcomes, namely short-term operating performance, long-term market valuation, systematic risk, and total risk. Using an international sample of 1776 industrial firms over the years 2002–2025, we find superior financial performance in carbon-efficient (best-practice) firms. On average, a 0.6 higher carbon efficiency is associated with a 7.0% higher profitability and 0.13% lower systematic risk. In this respect, a promising feature of the DDF model used in this paper is that it can be readily extended to accommodate multiple sustainability factors with different measurement units.

References:

1. Максудова Ш.Я. Развитие и размещение машиностроительного комплекса Узбекской ССР с учетом экологических факторов [Текст]: автореф. дис. ...канд. экон. наук: 08.00.04; №176. Академия наук Узбекской ССР Совет по изучению производительных сил (Ташкент). - Ташкент, 1991. – с. <http://www.dslib.net/economika-regionov/razvitie-i-razmewenie-mashinostroitel'nogo-kompleksa-uzbekskoj-ssr-s-uchetom.html>
2. Шарипов К.А. Стратегия сравнительного анализа развития промышленного предприятия. ICFNDS 21: Труды 5-й Международной конференции по будущим сетям и распределенным системам, Декабрь 2021 г. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3508072.3508122>
3. Murodov B.X., Sharipov K.A. Ko'mir sanoati korxonalarini rivojlantirishning zamonaviy xolati va ularga tasir etuvchi omillar. 2022/4/12. том 1. IIIIV-shuba. Страницы 292-295. Andijon. wtwinrar And MII, 2022. 6576.
4. Murodov B.X., Sharipov K.A. Ko'mir sanoati korxonalarini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy iqtisodiy mexanizmlarining samaradordik ko'rsatkichlari va ularni baholash. 2022/4/22. proceedings of the conference II-international scientific and scientific-technical conference «problems and prospects of innovative technique and technology in agri-food chain» Part 2. Страницы 554.
5. Murodov B.X., Sharipov K.A. Makro va mikroiqtisodiy sektor ekologiyani rivojlantirishga hissa qo'shadigan korxonalarni iqtisodiy tashkil etishning asosiy mexanizmlaridan biridir. "Роль инновационных методов и технологий в

- обеспечении экологической устойчивости" международный научный и наунотехнический собрание. Том-1. Страница 161. 2022/9/11. Ташкент.
6. Аллаева Г.Ж. Факторы повышения экономической эффективности при внедрении инновационных технологий на предприятиях тэк республики Узбекистан. Экономика и инновационные технологии, (3), 2016. с 123–129. извлечено от https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/economics_and_innovative/article/view/8791.
7. Алимукхамедова Н.Б. Детерминанты развития бизнеса: важность микрофинансирования для стартапов. Международная конференция по бизнесу и технологиям, 2021 г.
8. Мурадов Б.Х. Технические направления в промышленных аспектах в экономической грамотности для повышения потенциала молодежи в узбекистане для научных исследований. Electron ilmiy jurnal: Research and education, 4(3), 69-76, issn: 2181-3191, 2025. <https://zenodo.org/records/1516442>.
9. Мурадов Б.Х. Зарубежный опыт конкурентоспособность региональной экономики и перспективы национальных топливно-энергетических секторов-потребителей в угольной промышленности. International scientific journal "Interpretation and researches" 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14601115>.
10. Мурадов Б.Х. Еқилғи-энергетика тармоқлари саноати корхоналарининг рақамлаштириш ва ташкилий-иқтисодий механизмларини ривожланишининг такомиллаштириш «саноат 5» даражасида. International conference on developments in education sciences and humanities, canada. 2022 y. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6913315>.
11. Khujayev I.A. Modern trends in the development of the global textile industry// Global textile industry development trends. Warsaw-2021.
12. Хўжаев И.А. Енгил саноат корхоналарида ишлаб чиқариш харажатлари ва уларни камайтириш йўллари// Иқтисод ва молия. ISSN 1645-2025. 2021й. 3-сон
13. Хўжаев И.А. Определение эффективности издержек производства// Экономика и предпринимательство № 8 2020 г. 1256-1259 бетлар.